

THE EFFECT OF SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION ON SEARCH RESULTS: THE SEO EFFECT PROJECT*

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INTRODUCTION

On search engine result pages (SERPs), numerous actors can influence the visibility of results, one of them being search engine optimization (SEO). SEO is a multi-billion-dollar industry and defined as “the practice of optimizing web pages in a way that improves their ranking in the organic search results” [1]. Despite this importance, little is known about its impact on result rankings and user perspective on SEO, which is what our project SEO Effect¹ addresses. The project has components that focus on *users* and *SERPs* (Fig. 1), yet they are directly related to each other. In the following, we will outline how we have approached the project goal.

Figure 1: Project parts within the SEO Effect project.

MAJOR RESULTS

Expert interviews

As a basis for further project parts, we conducted expert interviews with stakeholder groups involved in search engine rankings: Search engine optimizers, content managers, and online journalists [2]. The interviews aimed to gather assessments of user perspectives regarding SEO. The interviewees assumed that SEO is barely known to the users and that the user opinions of SEO strongly depend on their SEO knowledge. From these assumptions, hypotheses were derived for the online survey described later. The interviews also served the SERPs part of the project, providing us with valuable clues on how SEO can be identified on websites.

Measurement of the SEO effect

We developed a multidimensional approach to make the SEO effect measurable and implemented this approach in a software tool that detects on a URL whether SEO measures have been taken [3]. For our approach, we use a model of $n = 48$ indicators based on an extensive literature

review and the aforementioned interviews with SEO experts [2]. The model is the basis for a decision tree classifier to determine the probability of SEO.

Representative online survey

We conducted a representative online survey with $n = 2,012$ German Internet users to get insights into the user perspectives on SEO [4, 5]. The results widely confirm the assumptions from the interviews. Less than half (43%) of Internet users know that ranking improvement is possible outside of paid ads, and only 8% are familiar with the term “SEO.” Due to this ignorance, SEO was rarely associated with organic results on SERP screenshots. With increasing knowledge of SEO, a more positive opinion could be observed. In the laboratory study described later, we revisited some elements of the survey, such as querying the SEO knowledge.

Analysis of health-related queries

We applied our approach to determine the probability of SEO on several datasets. One of our evaluation was conducted in preparation for our laboratory study. This involved automated analysis of $n = 318$ health-related search queries with a total of $n = 22,426$ search results from Google. The analysis showed that 32.6% of the search results were most probably optimized, 46.8% were probably optimized, and 20.7% were (probably) non-optimized. In terms of result positions, the distribution of optimized and non-optimized documents is equally distributed.

Laboratory study

The aim of the laboratory study is to investigate *whether* and *which* quality differences users perceive between optimized and non-optimized websites. Thus, this study brings together results of both project parts and consisted of evaluations of website quality based on various criteria (e.g., trustworthiness, expertise) plus think aloud protocols. The results show that (probably) non-optimized websites are rated as having a higher level of *expertise* than optimized websites. This assessment is independent of the subjects’ SEO knowledge and was mainly justified with the competent and reputable appearance of the operator in the case of non-optimized websites (e.g., websites of ministries).

CONCLUSION

Both subprojects have directly benefited from each other by triangulation of methods. The structure of our project thus proved to be fruitful, as we were able to examine the SEO effect from multiple angles. Further questions and starting points for follow-up projects are derived from the results. These include the influence of SEO on users’ knowledge acquisition and the development of a more differentiated SEO classification.

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¹ <https://searchstudies.org/research/seo-effekt/>

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Li, M. Lin, Z. Lin, and B. Xing, "Running and Chasing -- The Competition between Paid Search Marketing and Search Engine Optimization," in *2014 47th Hawaii Int. Conf. on System Sciences*, Waikoloa, HI, January 2014, pp. 3110–3119. doi: 10.1109/HICSS.2014.640.
- [2] S. Schultheiß and D. Lewandowski, "'Outside the industry, nobody knows what we do' SEO as seen by search engine optimizers and content providers," *J. Doc.*, vol. 77, no. 2, pp. 542–557, Dec. 2020. doi: 10.1108/JD-07-2020-0127.
- [3] D. Lewandowski, S. Sünkler, and N. Yagci, "The influence of search engine optimization on Google's results: A multi-dimensional approach for detecting SEO," in *WebSci '21: Proc. 13th ACM Conference on Web Science*, June 2021, to be published. doi: 10.1145/3447535.3462479.
- [4] S. Schultheiß and D. Lewandowski, "Misplaced trust? The relationship between trust, ability to identify commercially influenced results and search engine preference," *J. Inf. Sci.*, May 2021. doi: 10.1177/01655515211014157.
- [5] S. Schultheiß and D. Lewandowski, "(Un)bekannte Akteure auf der Suchergebnisseite? Ein Vergleich zwischen selbst eingeschätzter und tatsächlich vorhandener Suchmaschinenkompetenz deutscher InternetnutzerInnen," in *Information between Data and Knowledge. Information Science and its Neighbors from Data Science to Digital Humanities. Proc. 16th Int. Symposium of Information Science (ISI 2021)*, Regensburg, Germany, March 2021, pp. 218–246. doi: 10.5283/epub.44946.